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Halogen Bond-Driven Reversible Thermochromism in a Two-Dimensional Hybrid Perovskite

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ABSTRACT

Metal halide perovskites (MHPs) represent a versatile platform capable of accommodating new chemical design schemes for the development of innovative stimuli-responsive materials. In this work, we highlight that halogen bond (XB) can be exploited as a supramolecular tool to reversibly promote a single-crystal phase transition, which regulates the properties of a two-dimensional MHP under a low-energy thermal stimulus. By employing 2-iodoethylammonium (2IEA⁺) as a telechelic hydrogen- and XB donor tecton, we demonstrate that modulating the strength of the XBs through an external stimulus induces reversible cation isomerization, which in turn drives a phase transition from a Dion–Jacobson-like to a Ruddlesden–Popper-like stacking motif. This XB-driven mechanism allows the controllable and reversible thermochromism as well as heat switchable birefringence in MHPs, opening new avenues to further broaden the application landscape of this exciting class of materials.

1 | Introduction

Stimuli-responsive materials (SRMs) that dynamically alter their shapes and chemical-physical properties in response to external, environmental stimuli are at the forefront of research and innovation. Their adaptive nature enables the design of devices with enhanced functionalities and efficiencies, paving the way for a wide range of applications, including smart coatings and windows, on-demand drug delivery systems, artificial muscles, information storage, sensors, and optoelectronic devices, among others [1–3]. The rational design of reconfigurable SRMs with predictable responses requires that materials exhibit at least two stable states, which can be switched one into the other upon application of the external stimulus. Achieving this requires precise manipulation and control over the structure at the molecular and

intermolecular levels. In this context, noncovalent interactions (NCIs), due to their dynamic and reversible nature, offer an easy and cost-effective assembling method for designing adaptive materials with multiple response modes and logical control features [4, 5].

In the palette of NCIs available to chemists, the halogen bond (XB), i.e., the attractive interaction involving halogen atoms as electrophilic recognition sites, has been widely recognized as a versatile and efficient self-assembling tool in materials science and crystal engineering [6]. Its unique features, e.g., directionality, tunability, hydrophobicity, and variable XB-donor atom size, have enabled the design of sophisticated supramolecular functional systems for a wide range of applications [7]. In particular, these features have proven successful for developing XB as a new

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platform for engineering luminescent SRMs [8, 9], thermoresponsive shape-memory polymers [10, 11], self-healing liquid crystalline elastomers [12], and photoresponsive materials [13, 14].

Recently, XB has also been successfully exploited in the field of metal halide perovskites (MHPs), thanks to the rich halogen chemistry displayed by this kind of material, resulting in the useful control of their packing, improving their stability, and reducing surface trap states [15, 16]. Nowadays, XB-based supramolecular strategies are under the spotlight as efficient tools to modulate the crystallization of perovskite films and extend operational lifetime of devices thereof [17, 18]. MHPs are, in fact, structurally complex materials that exhibit a rich variety of polymorphic transitions upon exposure to low-energy external inputs, such as heat, pressure, vapors, or light, with drastic changes of their optical and electronic properties [19]. Such transitions often occur under device working conditions and are regarded as critical drawbacks for applications in solar cells and light-emitting diodes. As a consequence, research efforts are, on one side, focusing on suppressing phase transitions to obtain stable structures [20, 21]. On the other side, however, if controlled properly, these structural transitions could be exploited for the design of new, low-energy input SRMs, opening the way to a plethora of high-end applications [22–28]. While the use of XB for suppressing phase transitions in MHP-based devices is becoming increasingly popular, to the best of our knowledge, there are no examples, yet, of stimuli-responsive MHPs under XB control.

Here we report a crystal engineering-based design strategy to control phase transitions and subsequent optical responses in two-dimensional (2D) MHPs by exploiting the 2-iodoethylammonium cation ($2IEA^+$) as a telechelic hydrogen- (HB) and halogen- (XB) bond donor tecton [29, 30]. Upon application of a low-energy stimulus, such as increasing temperature, the weaker XB could selectively be “switched off”, transforming the bidentate cation (both XB- and HB-active) into a monodentate one (HB-only active), thereby promoting the crystal-to-crystal phase transition from Dion–Jacobson-like (DJ-like) to Ruddlesden–Popper-like (RP-like) perovskite (Figure 1), resulting in a material color change. Moreover, preliminary analyses revealed that the reported system also shows a marked heat-switching birefringence, thereby offering an additional handle for finely tuning the optical response of the investigated materials. Our results demonstrate that an XB-based crystal engineering strategy can successfully be pursued in the design of next-generation thermochromic perovskite materials.

2 | Results and Discussion

Generally, for 2D MHPs, diammonium cations drive the formation of DJ-like phases, where adjacent inorganic layers are held together in perfect alignment (0,0 offset), by one single layer of organic dications, thanks to the charge-assisted HB between the ammonium termini and the halide ions in the

FIGURE 1 | DJ-Like and RP-Like Structural Motifs and XB-Mediated Phase Switching in 2D MHPs. (a) Dion–Jacobson-like (DJ-like) and (b) Ruddlesden–Popper-like (RP-like) inorganic layer arrangement of two-dimensional hybrid organic–inorganic metal halide perovskites (2D MHPs), originating from the use of alkylammonium cations; (c) XB-controlled phase transition between DJ-like and RP-like motifs by utilization of a bidentate organic ammonium cation (both XB- and HB-active).

corner-sharing metal-halide octahedra (Figure 1a) [31]. On the contrary, monoammonium cations promote the formation of RP-like phases featuring a bilayer of organic cations between two adjacent inorganic layers [31]. Due to repulsion between organic cations, adjacent inorganic layers are offset by one-half of the M-X-M (M = metal, X = halogen) distance along both axes perpendicular to the stacking direction ($\frac{1}{2}$, $\frac{1}{2}$ offset) (Figure 1b). Due to their layered structure, DJ-like and RP-like MHPs exhibit greater pressure sensitivity than 3D perovskites and have recently gained attention for their mechanochromic behavior [32]. Their optoelectronic and transport properties can be easily and reversibly tuned without changing the composition, but manipulating their crystal structure through mechanical stimuli, already under mild pressure regimes (<1 GPa). Thus, we reasoned that reversible DJ-like \leftrightarrow RP-like conversion could be activated by physically cross-linking the halogen sites of adjacent inorganic layers by two discrete intermolecular interactions of different nature and strength, HB and XB, facilitated by the same organic cation. The weaker interaction, in this case the XB, could then be switched off by a low-energy external input, such as heat, thus promoting a conformational change of the cations, layer shifting, and subsequent DJ \leftrightarrow RP transformation (Figure 1c).

2.1 | Material Design

The selection of the organic cation is of paramount importance for the development of stimuli-responsive 2D perovskites under XB control. Through data mining in the Cambridge Structural Database [33] (Figure S1 and Table S1), we found Sourisseau et al. [34], who reported the 2-iodoethyl-1-ammonium (2IEA⁺) cation giving combined XB and HB at the organic-inorganic interface of hybrid perovskites. 2IEA⁺ is the shortest reported XB-donor cation able to promote the formation of a 2D perovskite composed of layers of corner-sharing [PbI₆]⁴⁻ octahedra with a DJ-like stacking motif and displaying iodine-iodine contacts between the iodine-terminus of the organic cation (I_{org}) and the apical iodine atoms (I_{ap}) of the inorganic network. Interestingly, 2EIA⁺ and a series of its superior homologs have also recently been used as a strategy to suppress low-temperature phase transitions [35, 36] in 2D MHPs, thanks to XB occurrence [37, 38] between I_{ap} of the inorganic network and the I_{org} of the organic cations. Being undercoordinated, the I_{ap} sites carry a surplus of electron density that can be electrostatically managed by the positively charged σ -hole emerging on the I_{org}. In this way, ω -iodoalkylammonium cations behave as bidentate species stabilizing the interstitial space defined by the corner-sharing octahedra through charge-assisted HB between the I sites in the inorganic layers and the ammonium terminus, and coordinating the I_{ap} in the inorganic layers through XB via the iodine-terminus.

Interestingly, investigating the single crystal structure reported for the 2(IEA)₂PbI₄ perovskite [34], we found that the 2IEA⁺ cations between metal-halide layers adopt an anti-conformation. Conversely, when iodine is substituted by bromine or chlorine, the syn-conformation of cations is preferred, and the XB interaction is absent [34]. Density functional theory (DFT) electronic structure calculations on the isolated 2XEA⁺ cations (X = Cl, Br, or I) revealed an energy stabilization for the syn-conformation of 2ClEA⁺ and 2BrEA⁺ cations, attributed to intramolecular N-H...X HB. In contrast, the 2IEA⁺ syn and anti-conformers were

predicted to be nearly iso-energetic (Table S2), so that a higher conformational flexibility of 2IEA⁺ with respect to 2ClEA⁺ and 2BrEA⁺ can be surmised. Additionally, a σ -hole - quantified as the maximum value of the molecular surface electrostatic potential ($V_{s, \max}$) - on X atom in the anti-conformers, was calculated to be 59.4, 64.8, and 70.9 kcal/mol for Cl, Br, and I, respectively, as expected on the basis of the increasing halogen atom polarizability (Figure S2). A higher σ -hole value may promote a stronger XB between the apical iodine on inorganic octahedra and X_{org}, which may be related to the different orientation of iodine cations in the 2(XEA)₂PbI₄ perovskite structures with respect to chlorine and bromine, even if other contributions to the structure stabilization, such as lattice strain, cannot be fully ruled out. The peculiar features of 2IEA⁺ cation further strengthen our idea of exploiting XB for handling phase transitions in 2(IEA)₂PbI₄ 2D perovskites through a controllable isomerization of the embedded organic cations.

2.2 | Synthesis and Thermochromic Behavior of (2IEA)₂PbI₄ MHP

While in all of the previous studies [29, 30, 34, 35, 38, 39], 2-iodoethylammonium iodide (2IEA-I) was directly produced in situ in the concentrated hydriodic acid solutions used for the perovskite synthesis, and never isolated, we obtained it as a stable pale-yellow crystalline salt that can be isolated and long-stored under ambient conditions. 2IEA-I was fully characterized by ¹H-, ¹³C-NMR, ESI-mass spectrum (MS), Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), and X-ray diffraction (XRD) techniques (Figures S3-S7). Single-crystal (SCXRD) analysis (Table S3) carried out at low temperature (200 K) revealed that 2IEA-I crystallizes in the monoclinic P21/c space group and was phase pure, as evidenced by powder XRD (Figure S8). The cation is well ordered and adopts a + *syn clinal* (+ *sc*) conformation, according to the Klyne-Prelog terminology (Figure S9), stabilized by an intramolecular HB involving the ammonium terminus and the C-bound iodine atom (N⁺...I distance = 3.468 Å). The I-anion is at the center of a slightly distorted seesaw coordination geometry surrounded by four N⁺ ions with -N⁺...I distances ranging 3.513–3.658 Å. A fifth coordination arises from the interaction with the C-bound I, which results in a rather weak XB, -C-I...I-distance 4.028 Å (~4% shorter than the sum of vdW, 1.98 Å, and Pauling, 2.20 Å, radii for I and I, respectively) and -C-I...I-angle 156.72°. A sixth coordination also arises from the interaction with one of the hydrogens of the -CH₂-I moiety of a nearby cation.

In order to study whether increased temperature would affect the NCIs observed in the 2IEA-I crystal, we also ran the SCXRD analysis at 300 K (Table S4). In this condition, instead, the cation adopts a - *sc* conformation (Figure S9) with a less distorted pentacoordinate I anion (-N⁺...I distances ranging 3.525–3.673 Å), where the previously observed weak XB disappeared. These changes demonstrate the high conformational flexibility of 2IEA⁺, and that the XB in these systems can be switched on and off with temperature.

The (2IEA)₂PbI₄ perovskite was synthesized by refluxing a 7:1 HI/H₃PO₂ aqueous solution containing 2IEA-I and PbI₂ (Figure 2a). Notably, (2IEA)₂PbI₄, whose stoichiometry was determined by single crystal analysis, was consistently isolated as

FIGURE 2 | Synthesis and thermochromic behavior of $(2\text{IEA})_2\text{PbI}_4$ crystals. (a) Synthesis of $(2\text{IEA})_2\text{PbI}_4$ crystals and photographs of the reaction pot at 390 K, 360 K, and 300 K showing the thermochromic behavior of the reaction mixture; (b) Optical microscope images of an individual crystal at 360 K and 300 K, highlighting the heat-induced color change; (c) DSC graphs of the $(2\text{IEA})_2\text{PbI}_4$ crystals for two consecutive heating-cooling cycles.

the sole product, irrespective of the $2\text{IEA}:\text{I}:\text{PbI}_2$ stoichiometric ratio employed for the synthesis, ranging from 1:1 to 4:1. Upon slowly cooling the reaction mixture, we noted the formation of an orange–red precipitate at 360 K, which turned yellow–orange at room temperature. The obtained plate-like crystals were observed at an optical microscope on a hot stage under polarized light, verifying that isolated yellow–orange crystals at room temperature turned orange–red at 360 K within a few seconds. Furthermore, no shape changes were observed, and the original color was restored upon cooling, which hinted at a reversible crystal-to-crystal phase transition (Figure 2b).

Temperature onset, energetics, and reversibility of the phase transition were assessed by DSC. The DSC profile on heating displayed quite an energetic endothermic transition ($\Delta H^\circ = 9.44$ kcal/mol) at 346 K (evolution of Phase 2), and an exothermic transition at 309 K on cooling (recovery of Phase 1), being reproducible in a consecutive heating-cooling run (Figure 2c). This behavior was highly reproducible over consecutive heating-cooling cycles with no degradation observed even after 75 cycles (Figure S16), thereby confirming the nondestructive and reversible nature of the

transition. However, there is a notable hysteresis of 30 K, whereas for reported nonhalogenated long-chain alkylammonium-based MHPs, the hysteresis is in the range of 2–20 K [40–44]. The thermal stability of the crystals was probed by TGA and was found to be stable up to 400 K (Figure S10).

The two crystalline phases were also studied by variable-temperature solid-state cross-polarization magic angle spinning (CP-MAS) ^{13}C -NMR to understand the nature of the observed transition. The ^{13}C CP-MAS NMR spectrum of Phase 1 (300 K) is consistent with the presence of $\text{I}-(\text{CH}_2)_2-\text{NH}_3^+$ entities as described by Sourisseau et al. [34], showing only one set of signals (44.7 ppm and 2.7 ppm) corresponding to the two carbon atoms of the 2IEA^+ cation (Figure S11). However, approaching the transition temperature (346 K), two new sets of downfield-shifted signals were evident, and, after a period of thermal equilibration inside the NMR probe (1 h at 346 K), the Phase 1 peaks disappeared completely. The new sets consisted of two peaks each at lower (3.74 and 5.21 ppm) and higher (45.5 and 46.4 ppm) frequencies in a 1:1 ratio, which demonstrates the coexistence of two isomeric 2IEA^+ cations in the high-temperature Phase 2. Upon cooling to room temperature, only the typical signals of pure Phase 1 are observed again, demonstrating the complete reversibility of the phase transformation. The back-isomerization of the 2IEA^+ cation might explain the phase transition observed in DSC.

2.3 | Thermally Induced Crystal-To-Crystal Transitions In $(2\text{IEA})_2\text{PbI}_4$ MHP

SCXRD studies at 300 K (Phase 1) and 360 K (Phase 2) allowed us to unveil the exact nature of the observed phase transition. In Phase 1, the lattice parameters are $a = 12.7329(4)$ Å, $b = 8.7287(3)$ Å, $c = 8.7455(3)$ Å; $\alpha = 90^\circ$, $\beta = 97.706(3)^\circ$, $\gamma = 90^\circ$, which confirmed the structure already reported by Sourisseau et al. [34], and described as orange crystals. All 2IEA^+ cations are in perfect anti-periplanar ($\pm ap$) conformation (torsion angle $\sim 180^\circ$), while the inorganic layers adopt a DJ-like stacking motif (Figure 3a). The distances of the cation's nitrogen terminus from the four neighboring I_{ap} sites are 3.5, 3.6, 5.3, and 5.4 Å, revealing displacement (Figure S12). The distance between the I_{ap} site of the inorganic layers and the iodine terminus of the cation ($\text{C}-\text{I}_{org}\cdots\text{I}_{ap}$) is 3.894 Å ($\sim 6\%$ shorter than the sum of vdW and Pauling radii for I and I, 6 respectively), with a $\text{C}-\text{I}_{org}\cdots\text{I}_{ap}$ angle of 177.96° , which is typical of a highly directional XB (Figure 3c).

In order to verify whether the transition was a crystal-to-crystal transformation, we exposed this yellow–orange single crystal to a hot nitrogen stream at 360 K. After reaching the temperature, the color change occurred suddenly, without any loss of crystallinity, confirming DSC and polarized optical microscopy results. This enabled the collection of the Phase 2 structure at 360 K (Table S5). Phase 2 is unprecedented and shows different lattice parameters [$a = 8.6583(5)$ Å, $b = 8.8341(4)$ Å, $c = 26.1785(15)$ Å; $\alpha = 90^\circ$, $\beta = 99.019(5)^\circ$, $\gamma = 90^\circ$], while retaining the same centrosymmetric $\text{P}2_1/c$ space group. Importantly, two different 2IEA^+ cations are found in the asymmetric unit ($Z' = 2$), in $-ap$ (torsion angle 168°) and $+sc$ conformations (torsion angle 52°) (Figure 4a–b), which explains the two sets of peaks observed in the high-temperature SSNMR spectrum of Phase 2. Now the inorganic layers are stacked

FIGURE 3 | Variable temperature XRD analysis of phase transition in $(2\text{IEA})_2\text{PbI}_4$ perovskite. (a,b) Powder XRD patterns of Phase 1 and Phase 2 obtained by the heat-induced single crystal to single crystal phase transition of $(2\text{IEA})_2\text{PbI}_4$ and illustration of the corresponding crystal packing; (c) Illustration of the supramolecular interactions between the cations and the inorganic network, highlighting the conformation of the cations, the XB formation in Phase 1 and the weakening or disruption of the XBs in Phase 2 of $(2\text{IEA})_2\text{PbI}_4$ single crystals; (d) Diagram showing the stacking offset of the inorganic slabs, namely the transformation from DJ-like to RP-like motif.

in an RP-like motif (Figure 3b, d), with the two 2IEA^+ cations that alternate along the inorganic plane and are arranged in pairs at the opposite sides of the interstitial space, resembling an alternating cation interlayer-like (ACI) motif [45] (Figure 3b-c and Figure S13). The $I_{\text{equatorial}}\text{-Pb-}I_{\text{equatorial}}$ dihedral angles are 149.47° and 153.41° (147.35° at 300 K), manifesting a slightly lower octahedral distortion. Accordingly, the octahedral rotation tilt is lower, and the cations are shifted toward the center of the interstitial space (Figure S13). Both conformers are displaced toward the out-of-plane direction. For the $-ap$ conformer, the $\text{C-I}_{\text{org}}\cdots\text{I}_{\text{ap}}$ distance is 3.892 \AA and the $\text{C-I}_{\text{org}}\cdots\text{I}_{\text{ap}}$ angle is 163.64° ($\sim 7\%$ shorter than the sum of vdW and Pauling radii for I and I₆ respectively). On the other hand, the $+sc$ -conformer displays a $\text{C-I}_{\text{org}}\cdots\text{I}_{\text{ap}}$ distance of 4.035 \AA ($\text{C-I}\cdots\text{I}_{\text{ap}}\text{-Pb}$ angle = 150.89°), indicating a very weakened XB, if any.

These observations for the XB involving cations in Phase 2 shall constitute a general design principle. In fact, in the benchmark 3D methylammonium lead triiodide (MAPbI_3) perovskite, it is well

established that the octahedral distortion decreases by increasing temperature, as a consequence of the weakening of the HB interactions between the methylammonium cation and the interstitial iodine sites [46]. In the case of $2\text{IEA}_2\text{PbI}_4$, the weakening of HBs and XBs allows the isomerization of the 2IEA^+ cations, which, thus, move toward the center of the interstitial space defined by the corner-sharing octahedra, providing a different chemical/structural environment at the interlayer, beyond the random order-disorder states met in long-chain alkylammonium-based HOIPs [42, 43].

The phase purity of the studied samples was assessed by powder (PXRD) studies on powder of $2\text{IEA}_2\text{PbI}_4$ at reflection and transmission geometry (Figure 4c-d and Figure S14). Upon heating, we observed a minor expansion along the a -axis, perpendicular to the corner-sharing $[\text{PbI}_6]^{4-}$ octahedral network, of Phase 1 ($\sim 0.6\text{ \AA}$), (Figure S15) prior to the phase transition, as evidenced by the shift of the 100 reflection (6.98°) of Phase 1 to lower angles, while the same was observed for the 200 (13.96°) and 400 (27.92°)

FIGURE 4 | Heat-induced conformational change of 2-iodoethylammonium cations and phase transition in $(2\text{IEA})_2\text{PbI}_4$. (a) Variable-temperature ^{13}C -CP MAS spectra of $2\text{IEA}_2\text{PbI}_4$ collected with a contact of 2 ms and a spinning speed of 8 kHz; (b) Illustration of the heat-induced conformational change of 2-iodoethylammonium cations between the two phases of $(2\text{IEA})_2\text{PbI}_4$, based on SCXRD. XRD spectra of Phase 1 (blue) and Phase 2 (red) of $(2\text{IEA})_2\text{PbI}_4$ crystal and powder samples under (c) reflection and (d) transmission geometries; (e) Graph showing the observed main XRD peak as a function of the applied temperature for $(2\text{IEA})_2\text{PbI}_4$ crystals in a heating-cooling cycle; (f) Illustration of the offset of the inorganic slabs at Phase 1 and Phase 2 of $2\text{IEA}_2\text{PbI}_4$, based on single crystal X-ray-diffraction.

reflections. After the phase transition, a family of new reflections associated with Phase 2, the 002 (6.79°), 004 (13.58°), and 008 (27.2°) reflections, as a result of a new unit cell, manifest the larger unit cell axis perpendicular to the corner-sharing $[\text{PbI}_6]^{4-}$ octahedral network and its different setting in accordance with the SCXRD studies. The evolution of the 200-reflection peak ($2\theta = 21^\circ$, $d = 4.3\text{ \AA}$) is associated with the increase in the in-plane order of the inorganic slabs due to the lower octahedral distortion. To confirm the reversibility of the phase transition, we performed a variable temperature XRD study of the crystalline sample, in a heating/cooling cycle (Figures S17–18). On heating, the crystal lattice is gradually expanding. Approaching the onset temperature,

the two phases coexist and, finally, Phase 2 dominates the spectrum, which confirms that the $2\text{IEA}_2\text{PbI}_4$ crystals interchange between the DJ-like stacking motif and the RP-like motif in a nondestructive and reversible manner (Figure 4f). During the cooling cycle, we detected the same phase transition hysteresis observed in DSC (Figure 4e). Upon cooling to room temperature, the initial signature of Phase 1 is fully restored. Notably, XRD patterns for $2\text{IEA}_2\text{PbI}_4$ crystals after the completion of the 75th heating-cooling cycle (Figure S16) further demonstrate that the transition is fully reversible and preserves the material integrity. In addition, the compound exhibits excellent long-term stability under ambient conditions for over 2 years, as confirmed by DSC

measurements and SCXRD and PXRD analyses (Figures S27-29 and Table S7).

2.4 | Electronic Structure and Bond Analysis

First-principles calculations have been carried out to investigate the electronic structures and bond pattern of Phase 1 and Phase 2 of $2\text{IEA}_2\text{PbI}_4$ crystals. To obtain an accurate description of the electronic structure of these compounds, calculations were carried out by the HSE functional including spin-orbit coupling on the PBE-optimized geometries [47, 48]. The computed electronic band structure (Figure S19 and Figure S20) points out a direct bandgap at the Γ point for both phases, with a value of 2.43 and 2.24 eV, respectively, for Phase 1 and Phase 2. The observed red shift in the energy gap from Phase 1 to Phase 2 of 0.19 eV aligns well with experimental data and nicely reflects the reduced distortion of the octahedral units in Phase 2, associated with the weakening of XB and HB interactions [49, 50]. PDOS analysis (Figure 5a,b and Figure S21) confirms the typical electronic structure of 2D MHPs [50–52], with the valence band (VB) and conduction band (CB) edges mainly derived from inorganic I 5p

and Pb 6p orbitals, respectively. The atomic orbitals of 2IEA^+ lie at ca. 1.0 and 1.5 eV below and above the edges, respectively, indicating no direct contribution of cations to states near the band edges. However, the energy level of inorganic I 5p orbitals is strongly affected by XB interactions, and in Phase 1, the I_{org} atom contributes to the DOS at 0.5 eV below the VB edge, with a consistently greater intensity than in Phase 2. This peculiar feature may stem from a stronger coupling of the organic cation with the inorganic octahedra, promoted by the XB present in Phase 1, potentially enhancing hole hopping within the VB.

The result of the NCI analysis between the 2IEA^+ cation - both the anti (Phase 1) and syn (Phase 2) conformers - and the inorganic I_{ap} atom, is reported in Figure 5c,d. Plots of reduced density gradient (RDG) versus the electron density (ρ) for the $2\text{IEA}-\text{I}_{\text{ap}}$ moieties exhibit the characteristic feature of spikes in the low-energy, low-density region, a typical footprint of NCIs. The isodensity surfaces (inset of Figure 5a,b) allow us to identify an attractive ($\lambda_2 < 0$) noncovalent region about midway between I_{org} and I_{ap} , which can be associated with the XB within the NCI framework. The weakening of the XB interaction for the syn versus anti-conformer is pointed out by

FIGURE 5 | Projected density of states (PDOS, HSE-SOC level) of (a) Phase 1 and (b) Phase 2; solid/dash-dotted/dotted lines correspond to inorganic/organic/ I_{org} contributions, E_g = energy gap; the insets show the gradient isodensity surface ($\rho = 0.5$ a.u.). RDG map versus $\text{sign}(\lambda_2)\rho$ of Phase 1 anti (c) and phase 2 syn (d) $2\text{IEA}-\text{I}_{\text{ap}}$ moieties; BE identifies the binding energy between the 2IEA^+ cation and the I_{ap} anion.

the shift of the characteristic peak toward zero ρ value on the RGB plot, in agreement with the XB geometrical parameters, as discussed above. The isodensity surface for the syn moiety allows us to correlate the second spike, at more negative ρ values, with the intramolecular N-H...X HB (green color), and the third spike at positive ρ values with steric repulsion (red color) between the I_{org} atom and the ammonium head. The computed binding energies confirm an energy stabilization of the anti-conformer (-2.94 kcal/mol), enabling XB, versus the syn conformer (-1.96 kcal/mol), enabling steric repulsion besides HB, while the XB is essentially inhibited. It is worth noting that, even if the isolated syn cation, showing intramolecular HB, has a stronger I σ -hole with respect to the isolated anti cation (Vs, max = 80.93

vs. 70.88 kcal/mol), it cannot engage a XB interaction with the I_{ap} because of the rigidity imposed by the inorganic framework.

Finally, we determined the charge carrier effective mass along high-symmetry directions of the 2D reciprocal space at the Γ -point, see Table S6. In line with previous studies [29, 53–55], we generally found lower masses for electrons than holes. This difference arises from the distinct atomic orbital hybridizations involved: I 5p–Pb 6s for the VB and I 6p–Pb 6p for the CB. When considering the in-plane transport direction along the inorganic layer plane ($\Gamma \rightarrow B$, $\Gamma \rightarrow Z$), the electron and hole effective masses are almost identical for the two Phases. However, along diagonal transport directions and the stacking direction

FIGURE 6 | Photophysical properties of $(2IEA_2)_2PbI_4$. (a) Kubelka–Munk spectra of $2IEA_2PbI_4$ crystals. Red arrow indicates the red shift of the excitonic band; (b) Evolution of PL emission of $2IEA_2PbI_4$ crystals (measurement in the bulk). Blue line: Phase 1, Black line: phase coexistence, Red line: Phase 2; (c) Confocal PL emission of an individual $2IEA_2PbI_4$ crystal as a function of temperature; (d) Graph showing the observed maximum PL emission band (free-exciton recombination) as a function of the applied temperature for an individual $2IEA_2PbI_4$ crystal in a heating-cooling cycle; (e) Single crystal of $2IEA_2PbI_4$ under nonpolarized and orthogonally polarized light at 300, 346, and 353K; (f) Rotation of a single crystal of $2IEA_2PbI_4$ being in Phase 1 and Phase 2 under orthogonally polarized light.

($\Gamma \rightarrow A$, $\Gamma \rightarrow E$, $\Gamma \rightarrow M$), slightly lower effective masses are found for the high temperature Phase 2 structure with respect to Phase 1. This suggests enhanced charge carrier mobility in Phase 2, consistent with the observed energy gap trend. As expected, the charge effective masses along the out-of-plane stacking direction ($\Gamma \rightarrow Y2$) are infinite, due to the lack of dispersion in this direction. Nevertheless, a closer look at the dispersion energy band along the Γ -Y2 direction suggests a less flat band for Phase 1, especially for the VB, indicating a somewhat smaller hole effective mass. This feature nicely correlates with the slightly higher octahedra distortion in Phase 1.

2.5 | Photophysical Properties of (2IEA)₂PbI₄ MHP

The discrete color of the two phases accounts for different photophysical properties. The optical absorption spectra of 2IEA₂PbI₄ at variable temperature, recorded in diffuse reflectance mode, and the Kubelka–Munk functions are shown in (F(R)) (Figure 6). For Phase 1, the spectrum of 2IEA₂PbI₄ crystals displays the absorption edge (469 nm) and the main exciton (503 nm) (Figure 6a). The photoluminescence (PL) emission spectrum of Phase 1 displays three main bands at 496, 535, and 720 nm (PL quantum yield, Φ , equal to 0.9%, Table S7). Cooling to 200 K, the 720 nm emission band becomes dominant, hinting at trap or self-trap exciton recombination [49] (Figure S22 and Figure S23). Moreover, the long lifetime of the 720 nm emission (456 μ s, on average) suggests at its origin the presence of either long-lived dissociated exciton recombination or phosphorescence through organic cation triplet [56–61]. (Figure S22).

The three emissions were further investigated by time-resolved PL (Figure S24). The narrow 496 nm band (free-exciton recombination) has a short lifetime (160 ps, on average), and the 535 nm signal (associated with excitons from layer edges) [56] possesses a longer lifetime (290 ps, on average). Moreover, the long lifetime of the 720 nm emission (456 μ s, on average) supports the hypothesis of long-lived dissociated excitons recombination at its origin [54–56]. Examining an individual crystal by confocal PL spectroscopy, a narrow band at 496 nm, with a shoulder centered at 520 nm, previously ascribed to a surface/subsurface dual emission mechanism [59, 62], and a weak low-energy emission band at 720 nm, were evident (Figure S22). This emission profile resembles that of the sample in powder (Figure S25).

Focusing on Phase 2, the absorption band is redshifted by 13 nm (Figure 6a) with a narrower bandgap of 2.25 eV (2.37 eV for Phase 1), due to lower octahedral distortion [63, 64]. These data perfectly agree with the DFT analysis. In the emission spectrum of Phase 2, the band of the main exciton is also redshifted (by 16 nm), and so are the lower energy bands (Figure 6b). Implementing variable-temperature confocal PL studies (Figure 6c) on an individual (2IEA)₂PbI₄ crystal in a heating-cooling cycle, we witnessed a phase transition hysteresis of 30 K, as seen in DSC (Figure 6d and Figure S26). This is a broader temperature range, as compared to long-chain alkylammonium 2D haloplumbates (5 K) [42–46].

Finally, preliminary analysis revealed that Phase 2 also displayed a marked heat-switching birefringence [65]. Observing a single crystal under an optical microscope, the initial yellow–orange color at 300 K (Phase 1) gradually turns orange–red at 353 K

(Phase 2) (Figure 6e). Repeating the observation under orthogonally polarized light, Phase 2 exhibits high light extinction. To qualitatively address the birefringence of a single crystal, we imaged the Phase 1 and Phase 2 under orthogonally polarized light at different orientations by rotating the mounted sample (Figure 6f). Phase 2 exhibited positions of extinction, namely is an optically anisotropic phase. Birefringence is likely to emerge from the thermotropic phase transition between the DJ-like and RP-like motifs and the resulting lower octahedra distortion [65].

3 | Conclusion

In this work, we highlight the role of the XB in the reversible modulation of the thermal, structural, and photophysical properties of (2IEA)₂PbI₄, a 2D iodoplumbate hybrid organic–inorganic perovskite (2D MHP). Utilizing the bimodal 2-iodoethylammonium (2IEA⁺) cation, we control the interlayer XBs by applying heat as an external stimulus. Deactivation of XB allows the isomerization of the organic cations in the interlayer space, adopting an alternating motif of anti and gauche conformers, which in turn enables the conversion of the DJ-like 2D MHP into an RP-like stacking motif with lower octahedral distortion and narrower bandgap. Complementary thermal (DSC), structural (XRD, solid-state NMR), and photophysical (UV–vis, PL) studies confirm the thermotropic nature of the new phase of (2IEA)₂PbI₄ (Phase 2), which has distinct properties and can be reversibly accessed in consecutive heating-cooling cycles (up to 75 cycles!). In the field of MHP materials, this is the first, to the best of our knowledge, demonstration that XB can be exploited as a supramolecular tool to reversibly modulate single-crystal phase transitions and optical properties of MHP semiconductors under an external stimulus. The high directionality of XB, as well as its tunable strength and the increased hydrophobicity, are pivotal characteristics to control the structure-properties relationships in perovskites and access tailor-made functional materials.

4 | Methods

4.1 | Materials

Starting materials and solvents were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and used as received.

4.1.1 | Synthesis of 2-Iodoethylammonium Iodide, 2IEA-I

In a round-bottom flask equipped with a magnetic stir bar, a condenser, and a nitrogen inlet/outlet, ethanolamine (1.0 mL, 1 eq, 16.57 mmol) was added and cooled in an ice bath. Then, hydriodic acid (nonstabilized 57%wt aqueous solution, 57%, 4.37 mL, 2.0 eq, 33.14 mmol) was added dropwise. Then the mixture was heated until reflux, under nitrogen, for a total of 2h, and finally allowed to cool at room temperature. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure with a rotary evaporator until dry. Cold diethyl ether was added to collect the brown-colored solids, which were transferred to a sintered glass filter and filtered under vacuum. The isolated solid was further washed with cold diethyl ether on the filter until the washings were colorless. The final pale-yellow crystalline solid was dried in a vacuum chamber

at room temperature. Yield: 92% (4.56g). $^1\text{H-NMR}$, deuterium oxide (D_2O) δ 3.49 (s, 4H) ppm; $^{13}\text{C NMR}$, deuterium oxide (D_2O) δ 0.00 (s, 1C), 43.78 (s, 1C) ppm. ESI-MS: $m/z=172$ (M + 1). FT-IR: 514 cm^{-1} (s, C-I stretching).

4.1.2 | Synthesis of Bis(2-Iodoethylammonium) Lead (II) Tetra-Iodide, $(2\text{IEA})_2\text{PbI}_4$

In a round-bottom flask equipped with a magnetic stir bar, a condenser and a nitrogen inlet/outlet, PbI_2 (1eq, 3.3 mmol, 1.52 g), 57%wt aqueous solution of HI (7eq, 23.1mmol, 3.05 mL) and 50%wt aqueous solution of H_3PO_2 (1eq, 3.3mmol, 0.35 mL) were added, and the mixture was heated under nitrogen in a preheated oil bath at 50°C . The solution turned bright yellow, indicating the dissolution of PbI_2 . Subsequently, 2IEA-I (2eq, 6.6mmol, 1.97g) was added, and the mixture was heated to reflux for 10 min, furnishing a bright yellow solution. After the magnetic stir bar was removed, the heating was stopped, and the mixture was allowed to reach room temperature, immersed in the oil bath. The flask remained undisturbed for 8h. The yellow–orange plates were filtered through a sintered glass filter to remove the excess of the acids, then washed with cold ethyl acetate and finally dried in a vacuum chamber at room temperature. Yield: 85% (2.97g). SC and PXRD spectroscopy verified the structure and the phase purity of the isolated $(2\text{IEA})_2\text{PbI}_4$.

4.2 | General Procedures

4.2.1 | NMR Characterization

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ and $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ spectra in solution (D_2O) were recorded at room temperature with an AV400 Bruker Avance III spectrometer.

^{13}C and ^1H solid-state NMR experiments were carried out at 75.5 and 300.1 MHz, respectively, with a Bruker Avance Neo instrument operating at a static field of 7.04 T equipped with a 4 mm double resonance MAS probe. ^{13}C (^1H) ramped-amplitude CP experiments were performed at room temperature at a spinning speed of 8 kHz using a recycle delay of 4 s and a contact time of 2 ms. The 90° pulse for the proton was $2.5\ \mu\text{s}$. Variable temperature experiments have been performed in the range 300–346 K. Crystalline polyethylene was taken as an external reference at 32.8 ppm from TMS.

4.2.2 | Mass Spectrometry

MS was obtained on an ESI Ion Trap LC/MSn System (BRUKER Esquire 3000 PLUS).

4.2.3 | FT-IR

FT-IR spectra were recorded at room temperature with a Thermo Scientific Nicolet iS50 FT-IR spectrometer, equipped with iS50 ATR accessory (Thermo Scientific, Madison, USA).

4.2.4 | Thermal Characterization

TGA analyses were performed with a TA Q500 instrument. The samples were analyzed in a nitrogen atmosphere with a temperature ramp of 20 K min^{-1} .

DSC analyses were performed with a Mettler Toledo DSC823e instrument, using aluminum light $20\ \mu\text{L}$ sample pans, a temperature ramp of 10 K min^{-1} , and Mettler STARE software for calculations.

4.2.5 | Imaging Crystals

Crystal imaging was performed by an Olympus BX51 optical microscope equipped with a Linkam Scientific LTS350 heating stage and a Sony CCD-IRIS/RGB video camera.

4.2.6 | XRD Characterization

The WAXS profiles of the samples in transmission mode were studied with a Xeuss 3.0 UHR SAXS/WAXS system (Xenocs SAS, Grenoble, France) equipped with a GeniX 3D Cu K alpha radiation source ($\lambda \approx 1.54\ \text{\AA}$) and with in-vacuum motorized 3-axis Q-Xoom Eiger2 R 1M detector (Dectris Ltd., Switzerland) for 2D SAXS/WAXS data collection. The explored q range was $0.0015\ \text{\AA}^{-1} < q < 2.419\ \text{\AA}^{-1}$, where q is the absolute value of the scattering vector and is defined as $q = 4\pi/\lambda \cdot \sin(2\theta/2)$, and 2θ is the scattering angle. Measurements were performed under vacuum ($<0.1\text{ mbar}$), and the temperature of the samples was controlled by a multipurpose Peltier-type temperature stage (temperature range: 248–420K) operated by a Xenocs controller equipped with a water-cooling module (KOOLANCE EXT-440). Each sample was placed in a cavity composed of two aluminum foils sandwiching a rubber O-ring. The distance of the detector was 100 mm, and the spectrum accumulation time was 300 s at a High-resolution collimation mode.

The WAXS profiles of the samples in reflection mode were studied with a Bruker D8 diffractometer (transmission mode; Ge-monochromated $\text{CuK}\alpha 1$; $\lambda = 1.5406\ \text{\AA}$; Vantec detector covering 12° in 2θ ; 2θ range, 4° – 70° ; step size, 0.017°). For the variable temperature experiments, the crystals were heated at a rate of 0.01 K/sec from room temperature to a maximum of 360 K at 5–10K intervals. Before each measurement, the crystals were thermally equilibrated for 2 min. The data collected from 2θ range 5° – 50° , step size 0.024° , and exposure time 0.2 s/step (total exposure 6 min 25 s). All measurements performed at ambient pressure, air, and humidity.

SCXRD data were collected using a XtaLAB Synergy diffractometer, equipped with a HyPix detector and a $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ ($\lambda = 1.54184$) source. The temperature was controlled by an Oxford Cryostream 1000, utilizing liquid nitrogen and a dry nitrogen gas stream. Unit cell refinement, absorption correction, and data reduction were performed with CrysAlisPro 1.171.41.98a. All the structures were solved with the ShelXT [66] using the Intrinsic Phasing solution method, with Olex2 [67] as the graphical interface. The model was refined with ShelXL [68] using Least Squares minimization. Images of the refined structures were produced by the free version of Mercury software, developed by the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Center.

4.2.7 | Photophysical Characterization

The absorbance of the samples was calculated using the Kubelka-Munk function ($F(R)$) according to the following equations

$$R = \frac{R_{\text{sample}}}{R_{\text{standard}}} \quad (1)$$

$$F(R) = \frac{K}{S} = \frac{(1-R)^2}{2R} \quad (2)$$

where R is the reflectance of the sample for “infinite thickness” (sample thicknesses > 1 mm) equal to the ratio of the reflectance of the sample (R_{sample}) and reflectance of the standard material (R_{standard}), K and S are the absorption and scattering Kubelka-Munk coefficients, respectively.

Steady state and time-resolved fluorescence data were obtained using a FLS980 spectrofluorometer (Edinburgh Instrument Ltd). Emission spectra were corrected for background intensity and quantum efficiency of the photomultiplier tube. PL lifetime measurements were performed using an Edinburgh Picosecond Pulsed Laser (emitted wavelength 445 nm) (Edinburgh Instrument Ltd) and a microsecond flash Xe-lamp (60W, 0.1 ÷ 100 Hz) with data acquisition devices, time correlated single-photon counting and multi-channel scaling methods, respectively. Absolute PL quantum yield, Φ , was determined through a C11347 Quantaurus spectrometer (Hamamatsu Photonics K.K) as described by Suzuki et al. [69]

Microscopy fluorescence spectra were collected with a Nikon Eclipse TE2000-U inverted confocal microscope equipped with a Linkam LTS420 heating system, by exciting with a DAPI 405 nm laser and collecting the emission through an optical fiber connected to a NanoLog composed by an iH320 spectrograph equipped with a Synapse QExtra charge-coupled device. Time-resolved PL curves were fitted using a multi-exponential function:

$$I(\lambda, t) = \sum_{i=1}^m \alpha_i(\lambda) \exp\left(\frac{-t}{\tau_i}\right) \quad (3)$$

where m is the number of exponentials, $\alpha_i(\lambda)$ is the amplitude at wavelength λ , and τ_i is the lifetime of the component i . The quality of the fit was evaluated through the reduced χ^2 values. In case of multi-exponential decay, it was possible to define an average lifetime as:

$$\tau_{\text{av}} = \tau_{\text{av}} = \frac{\sum_{n=1}^m \alpha_n \tau_n^2}{\sum_{n=1}^m \alpha_n \tau_n}, \quad m = \text{multi-exponential decay number of the fit.}$$

4.2.8 | Computational Methods

DFT electronic structure calculations were carried out on the isolated 2EIA⁺ organic cations with the Gaussian09 program package [70], along with the B3LYP functional with Grimme D3 dispersion correction [71] and 6-31G* basis set, for all the atoms except iodine, for which the composite SDD basis set with the corresponding ECP was employed. The geometry optimizations were carried out in vacuo, followed by single-point energy calculations in water solvent with the self-consistent reaction field solvation together with the Polarizable Continuum Model [72]. Maxima and minima of the molecular surface electrostatic potential on the $\rho = 0.001$ au isodensity surface of each conformer were identified via the Multiwfn program [73]. Single-point energy calculations

were carried out on selected moieties extracted from the XRD 2IEA2PbI4 perovskite structures, including the 2EIA⁺ cation and the inorganic iodine atoms in close proximity to it. In addition to the estimation of the binding energies, an NCI study [74] was carried out to distinguish the presence of the XB interaction in Phase 1 and 2 upon 2EIA⁺ isomerization. The NCI method is based on the relationship of the reduced density gradient, RDG, s , and the electron density, ρ , according to the equation:

$$s(\vec{r}) = \frac{1}{2(3\pi)^{1/3}} \cdot \frac{|\nabla\rho(\vec{r})|}{\rho(\vec{r})^{4/3}} \quad (4)$$

Upon formation of a weakly bound complex, peculiar signals emerge in the NCI plot. The identification of an attractive or repulsive interaction is gained from the analysis of the Laplacian of ρ , which can be written using the 3 components along the 3 principal axes of maximal variation as:

$$\nabla^2\rho = \lambda_1 + \lambda_2 + \lambda_3, \lambda_1 \leq \lambda_2 < \lambda_3 \quad (5)$$

In line with common practise for weak interaction, the NCI method employs λ_2 to distinguish between bonded ($\lambda_2 < 0$) and nonbonded ($\lambda_2 > 0$) interactions, whereas the ρ value provides information about the interaction strength. This method is able to identify the presence of HB, XB, van der Waals interactions, and repulsive steric clashes [75]. On the (2IEA)₂PbI₄ perovskite structures, periodic DFT electronic structure calculations were performed in the planewave/pseudopotential formalism, as implemented in the Quantum Espresso suite program [76]. Starting from the XRD structures gained at various temperature values, geometry optimizations were carried out, relaxing only the hydrogen atomic positions, while keeping fixed both the cell parameters and the Pb, I, C, N atomic positions. For the atomic relaxation, we resorted to the generalized gradient approximation PBE functional [49] with DFT-D3 Van der Waals corrections and scalar relativistic ultrasoft pseudopotentials [77], with valence electrons from 2s, 2p for O, N, and C; 1s for H; 5s, and 5p for I; 6s, 6p, and 5d for Pb. Plane-wave basis set cutoffs for the smooth part of the wave functions and the augmented density were set to 50 and 400 Ry, respectively. For the electronic structure calculation, we instead shifted to norm-conserving pseudopotentials, including SOC, at the PBE level, with wave function and electronic density cutoffs of 60 and 240 Ry, respectively. In the case of Pb, 22 valence electrons were considered, by including the Pb 5s and 5p states, while for the other elements, pseudopotentials with the same number of valence electrons as in the US case were used. Hybrid calculations, SOC included, have also been considered by employing the HSE functional [47], with an exact exchange percentage equal to 0.43. This setup has been successfully used for the prediction of structural properties of 3D and 2D perovskites [78–80]. To reduce the computational effort, hybrid SOC calculations have been performed by using a plane wave cutoff of 60 Ry, without affecting the accuracy of the calculations. A k-point grid $3 \times 3 \times 1$ in the Monkhorst–Pack scheme was used, with 3 points along the two short periodic directions and 1 point along the long stacking direction. DOS calculation has been carried out using the hybrid HSE functional. Band structure calculation has been performed at the PBE-SOC level of theory, along high-symmetry directions of the relevant 2D reciprocal space at the Γ -point.

The Phase 2 axes have been rotated, with the plane stacking direction matching the *c*-axis, so that the reciprocal direction related to the plane stacking direction corresponds to Γ -Y2 in both Phases, and an easy comparison of the band dispersion is gained. Effective masses were extracted by fitting the curvature of the energy dispersion near the band edges, so that the more dispersive /flat the band near the edge, the lighter/heavier the effective mass is (see Table S6). 2D perovskites are characterized by an anisotropic conductivity: charge carriers are highly mobile within the inorganic layers, while they are essentially immobile in the stacking direction. As a result, low effective mass values are expected in the former case, while values approaching infinity are expected in the latter case.

Author Contributions

P.M. and G.C. jointly designed the project, supervised its execution, and secured funding. A.S. carried out the experimental work, collected most of the crystallographic data, and wrote the first draft of the manuscript. G.T. supervised the crystallographic analysis; E.C., D.M., and C.B. performed the photophysical studies, while S.B. conducted the solid-state NMR analysis. F.D.A., F.N., and T.M. led the computational analysis and theoretical discussion. All authors contributed to writing and revising the manuscript and approved the final version for publication.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

All data supporting the findings of this study are included within the article and its supplemental information and are also available from the authors upon request. CCDCs 2477300, 2477301 and 2477302 contain the supplementary crystallographic data for this paper. These data can be obtained free of charge from The Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre via www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/data_request/cif.

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Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information Section.